

High Performance and Fault Tolerant Techniques Used to Improve the Data Processing Performance in Big Data

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Abstract

Big data plays a major role in the real world. Every day the database access may be in increased manner. The size of the database is also increased as in terabytes. Different types of people in different places can access and store their data that are needed for their usage. Big data may contain a large volume of data. Everyone access data simultaneously. To retrieve the particular data from the large database is not easy. To avoid these types of problems, many of techniques are developed to extract the needed data in a large database. Sometimes the larger size of a database may lead to degrading the performance and also a chance for fault. To avoid these types of problems some of the techniques may be used that are Hadoop, MapReduce, HDFS, XHMI, Spark, locator, etc., In this paper a comparative study is done in the techniques, find which is used to produce high-performance data processing in big data. The speed of data processing is specified to find the best technique for high performance and fault tolerance capacity.

Keywords: Big data, Hadoop, MapReduce, stocator, HDFS.

Introduction

Big Data mining is the capability of extracting useful information from these large datasets or streams of data which were not possible before due to its volume, variety, and velocity. The extracted knowledge is very useful and the mined knowledge is the representation of different types of patterns and each pattern corresponds to knowledge. Data Mining is analyzing the data from different perspectives and summarizing it into useful information that can be used for business solutions and predicting the future trends. Mining the information helps organizations to make knowledge-driven decisions. Data mining (DM), also called Knowledge Discovery in Databases (KDD) or Knowledge Discovery and Data Mining, is the process of searching large volumes of data automatically for patterns such as association rules. It applies many computational techniques from statistics, information retrieval, machine learning and pattern recognition. Data mining extract only required patterns from the database in a short time span. Based on the type of patterns to be mined, data mining tasks can be classified into

summarization, classification, clustering, association and trends analysis. An enormous amount of data are generated every minute [1].

Big Data can be termed as the collection of large and complex datasets such that traditional data processing techniques are not able to process it. With its growing scope in three dimensions, i.e., volume, velocity, and variety, there is a necessity emerging as big data analytics which can be defined as the process of collecting, organizing, and analyzing large sets of datasets to discover and generate a useful pattern and other information. Whether it is a big enterprise, scientific laboratory, or any organization, all need big data analytics to increase their work efficiency and improve operations[2].

Big Data

Big Data is the word used to describe massive volumes of structured and unstructured data that are so large that it is very difficult to process this data using traditional databases and software technologies. The term “Big Data [5]” is companies who had to query loosely structured very large distributed data.

Figure Depicts the major properties of Big data.

The three main terms that signify Big Data have the following properties:

Volume: Many factors contribute towards increasing Volum streaming data and data collected from sensors etc.,

- Variety: Today data comes in all types of formats emails, video, audio, transactions, etc.,
- Velocity: This means how fast the data is being produced and how fast the data needs to be processed to meet the demand. The other two dimensions that need to consider concerning Big Data are Variability and Complexity [5].
- Variability: Along with the Velocity, the peaks.
- Complexity: Complexity of the data also needs to be considered when the data is coming from multiple sources. The data must be linked, matched, cleansed and transformed into required formats before actual processing. Technologies today not only support the collection of large amounts of utilizing such data effectively[3].

Literature Review

Hadoop: It is an open source technology used to store, access a large amount of data in a distributed fashion at a high degree of scalability and fault tolerance. Connecting single server to thousands of machines with data stored in local (local storage) and computation.[4]

MapReduce: Designed to process a large volume of data in parallel mode. In that, we have two functions in a separate map() and Reduce().Map()-perform filter and sort operations. Reduce()-Perform aggregation operation[4].

This technology may join with Hadoop to increase their performance in the next level. It is used to boost the performance.

Hadoop Distributed File System(HDFS): It is a java based file system. That can be used to provide high throughput access to application data. This may contain Master/Slave Structure. If the data are arranged in a distributed manner, then it is easy to access the relevant/needed data without delay. [5]

XHAMI(Extended HDFS and MapReduce Interface): It is used for large-scale image processing in mining. XHAMI developed with the combination of HDFS and MapReduce. XHAMI offers an extended library of HDFS and MapReduce to process the single large-scale images with high-level of abstraction over writing and reading the images. XHAMI makes an interface big data image processing in the cloud environment [6].

ST-Hadoop: It is a MapReduce framework that can be used to access big spatiotemporal data. It is a new idea of indexing, where the data are temporarily loaded and divided across computational nodes [7].

Spark: It is used on top of HDFS, and assurance speeds up to 100 times faster than the two-step MapReduce function. That allows data to load in memory and queried frequently, making it especially good for Machine Learning Algorithm.

Apache Spark: It is an open source cluster Computing framework. It emerges as a next-generation big data processing engine. It maintains MapReduce linear scalability and fault tolerance.

G-Hadoop: Extension of Hadoop MapReduce framework. It allows MapReduce task to run on multiple clusters. It simply reuses the user authentication and job submission mechanism of Hadoop.

Hive using Sqoop: It is used to increase the performance and optimization in Hadoop. Very fast it is loading the huge volume of relational data into big data warehouse. Fast query processing by increasing the throughput.

Stocator: High-performance object store connector for spark. Stocator takes advantage of object store semantics to achieve both high performance and fault tolerance. It eliminates rename paradigm by writing each output object to the object's file name. Where it is as much as 18 times faster compared to other data processing techniques [8].

Related Work

Apache Hadoop

A open-source software in Java is used majorly for distributed storage and processing of extremely large data sets on computer clusters. Apache Hadoop mainly coupled with a storage part (Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)) and a processing part (MapReduce). Splitting up of files into large blocks and distributing them on the nodes in the cluster is take care by Hadoop only. It is not the job of the programmer to do the distribution over the cluster, Hadoop itself looks into it. In Hadoop, the data processing is done with MapReduce, by transferring the program code to the nodes in parallel based on the data requirements of each node, i.e., the process code travels to the node.

The Hadoop framework is encapsulated with the following modules:

- Hadoop Common
- Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)
- Hadoop MapReduce.

Hadoop Distributed File System (HDFS)

The Hadoop File System (HDFS) offers the efficiency to store huge amounts of unstructured data reliably on commodity hardware. In spite of there are file systems with preferable performance, HDFS is an integral part of the Hadoop framework and has already reached the level of a beneficial standard. It has been designed for huge data files and is well suited for hastily ingesting data and agglomeration processing[10].

The Hadoop distributed file system (HDFS) is a distributed, scalable, and portable file-system written in Java for the Hadoop framework. Each node in a Hadoop instance typically has a single name node, and a cluster of data nodes form the HDFS cluster[5]. The situation is typical because each node does not require a data node to be present. Each data node serves up blocks of data over the network using a block protocol specific to HDFS[10].

MapReduce

The preparing column in the Hadoop biological system is the MapReduce structure. The system permits the specification of an operation to be applied to a huge data set, divide the problem and information, and run it in parallel. From an expert’s perspective, this can happen on various measurements. For example, a very large dataset can be reduced into a smaller subset where analytics can be connected. In a conventional information warehousing situation, this may involve applying an ETL operation on the data to produce something usable by the analyst. In Hadoop, these kinds of operations are composed as MapReduce employments in Java. There are various larger amount dialects like Hive and Pig that make writing these programs easier. The outputs of these jobs can be written back to either HDFS or put in a customary information distribution center.

There are two capacities in MapReduce as follows :

Map: the function takes key/value pairs as input and generates an intermediate set of key/value pairs

Reduce: the function which merges all the intermediate values associated with the same intermediate key[11].

HDFS Architecture

Hadoop incorporates a fault-tolerant stockpiling framework called the Hadoop Distributed File System, or HDFS. HDFS can store huge amounts of information, scale up incrementally and survive the disappointment of noteworthy parts of the capacity framework without losing information. Hadoop creates clusters of machines and coordinates work among them. Clusters can be built with inexpensive PCs. If one fizzles, Hadoop keeps on working for the group without losing information or hindering work, by shifting work to the remaining machines in the cluster. HDFS manages storage on the cluster by breaking approaching records into pieces, called “squares,” and putting away each of the squares redundantly across the pool of servers. In the common case, Fig 4. HDFS stores three complete copies of each file by copying each piece to three different servers [11].

Figure Represent the Architecture of Hadoop

XHAMI – Extended HDFS and MapReduce

The extended software package of Hadoop for large-scale image processing/mining applications. XHAMI offers Software Development Kit for Hadoop-based large-scale domain-specific data-intensive applications designing. It provides high-level packages for data organization and for MR-based processing simplifying the development and quick application designing by hiding several low-level details of image organization and processing [6].

ST-HADOOP

A full-fledged MapReduce framework with native support for big spatiotemporal data. ST-Hadoop is a comprehensive extension to Hadoop that injects spatiotemporal data awareness inside Spatial Hadoop layers[7]. ST-Hadoop is an extension of a Hadoop framework that injects the spatiotemporal awareness in the code base of four layers inside Spatial Hadoop, namely, language, indexing, Map Reduce, and operations layers. The key point behind the performance gain of ST-Hadoop is the idea of indexing, where data are temporally loaded and divided across computation nodes.

G-HADOOP

G-Hadoop is a MapReduce implementation targeting on a distributed system with multiple clusters, such as a Grid infrastructure, a Cloud, distributed virtual machines, or a multi data center infrastructure. To share data across multiple administrative domains, G-Hadoop replaces Hadoop's native distributed file system with the Gfarm Grid file system. MapReduce applications in G-Hadoop are scheduled across multiple clusters using a hierarchical scheduling approach. The MapReduce tasks are firstly scheduled among the clusters using Hadoop's Dat aware scheduling policy and then among compute nodes using the existing cluster scheduler on the target clusters. G-Hadoop maintains the master/slave model of Hadoop, where the slave nodes are simple workers, while the master node accepts the jobs submitted by the user, splits the min to smaller tasks, and finally distributes the tasks to the slave nodes. The current G –Hadoop system reuses the Hadoop mechanisms for user authentication and job submission, which is actually designed for single cluster environments. The mechanism applies the Secure Shell(SSH)protocol to establish a secure connection between a user and the target cluster. This kind of mechanism is not suitable for a distributed environment, like Grid, which contains several large-scale clusters. In G-Hadoop, for example, an individual SSH connection has to be built between the user and every single cluster. This approach does not handle the system as a whole; rather it works separately with the systems components. Also, with the Hadoop security approach, a user must log onto each cluster inorder to be authenticated before being capable of using its resources for running MapReduce tasks.

This is undoubtedly a tedious task for the users. Therefore, a more general, system-wide solution is required to hide the architecture details of the system as well as to free the user from the burden[12]. Hive In Hive is data warehousing software that addresses how data is structured and queried in distributed Hadoop clusters. Hive is also a famous development environment that is used to write queries for data about the Hadoop environment. It endows tools for ETL operations and brings some SQL-like potential to the environment. Hive is a declarative language that is used to develop applications for the Hadoop environment, although it does not support real-time queries[13]. Sqoop The Sqoop as a front-end loader for big data. Sqoop is a command-line interface that makes easier in moving bulk data from Hadoop into relational databases and other structured data stores. Using Sqoop replaces the necessity to develop scripts to export and import data. In the common use case is to rehabilitation data from an enterprise data warehouse to a Hadoop cluster for ETL processing. Functional ETL on the commodity Hadoop cluster is resource efficient, while Sqoop provides a practical transfer method [13].

Comparison of Techniques Used for Data Processing

The below table explains about the various characteristics of techniques to increase data processing and identify fault tolerance.

Comparison of Big Data Processing Techniques to Increase the Performance

Technology	Description	Working	Performance /Speed	Fault Tolerance	Data Storage Formats	Compressing
Hadoop	Technique is used for data process	Data is stored in data blocks on the data nodes. A single name node tracks the data.	Performance is average compare to the previously used technology for data processing	Nil	Apache Avro is a data serialization technique for storing data	possible
MapReduce	Processing technique for distributed computing	Map takes set of data and convert into another set of data.	Performance is high comparing to hadoop	NIL	Tuples, key,value pairs,tables	Increase read write speed and reduce network overhead
Spark	Open source big data processing framework, build around speed,ease of use	Spark does not have own distributed file system. It uses memory instead of disk.	Performance is high comparing to Mapreduce, because it uses memory and also disk for processing but Mapreduce uses only disk for processing 100 times faster comparing to hadoop and Marreduce	Yes(using WAL-write Ahead Log-ging)	Many different file formats like plain text, XML,SQL[small files may give you better performance]	Splittable Compression
Stocator	A high performance storage connector	Enable spark to work directly on data stored in objectstorage system	Performance is 18 times faster than spark	Yes (highly fault tolerant)	Very large data files, object stores[using cloud object storage]	Compression is available for larger data files.

Conclusion

A big data processing plays an important role in the competitive world to solve the larger type of requirements. Larger types of structured and unstructured data are processed in big data. In this paper, the some of the technologies that are used to increase the data processing performance and provide fault-tolerant can be identified and that type of technologies are listed. In that, the technology called stocator is comparatively having higher performance than another one can be found. So that stocator is used for higher data processing and to find fault tolerance compare to other techniques. In the future, this technique may overcome many other problems also.

References

- A Perusal Of Big Data Classification And Hadoop Technology Nikhat Akhtar, Firoj Parweej, Yusuf Perweej ,International Transaction Of Electrical And Computer Engineers System, 2017, Vol. 4, No. 1, 26-38 Available Online At [Http://Pubs.Sciencedirect.com/Itces/4/1/4](http://Pubs.Sciencedirect.com/Itces/4/1/4) © Science And Education Publishing Doi:10.12691/Itces-4-1-4
- A Study Of Big Data Mining Techniques Used To Improve The Performance Of Large Data Processing Ms.G.Suganya Mca., Guest Lecturer,Department Of Computer Applications,Sri Akilandeswari Womens College,Wandiwash,India,ijrcce, ISSN(Online): 2320-9801 Vol. 5, Issue 7, July 2017
- A Survey On Big Data Privacy Using Hadoop Architecture Priyank Jain, Manasi Gyanchandani, Nilay Khare, Dhirendra Pratap Singh, Lokini Rajesh ,Cse Department Manit, Bhopal M.P India , Ijcsns International Journal Of Computer Science And Network Security, Vol.17 No.2, February 2017 148 Manuscript Received February 5, 2017 Manuscript Revised February 20, 2017
- Bareen Shaikh, Kavita Shinde, Sangeeta Borde, “Challenges Of Big Data Processing And Scheduling Of Processes Using Various Hadoop Schedulers: A Survey” International Journal Of Multifaceted And Multilingual Studies ,Volume-Iii, Issue-Xii Issn (Online):2350-0476
- Gil Vernik, Michael Factor, Elliot K., Pietro Michiardi, Francesco Pace” Stocator: A High Performance Object Store Connector For Spark” Acm Isbn 978-1-4503-5035-8/17/05.
- Issues, Challenges, And Solutions:Big Data Mining Jaseena K.U. And Julie M. David,Department Of Computer Applications,M.E.S College, Marampally, Aluva, Cochin, India
- Journal Of Computer And System Sciences 80 (2014) 994–1007 Contents Lists Available At Science direct Journal of computer and system sciences A security frameworking Hadoop for bigdata computing across distributed cloud data centres Jiaqizhaoa, Lizhewangb, Jietaoc,Jinjunchend, Weiyesunc, Rajivranjane, Joannakołodziejf, Achimstreitc, Dimitrios georga kopoulose www.Elsevier.Com/Locate/Jcss
- Louai Alarabi:” St-Hadoop: A Mapreduce Framework For Big Spatio-Temporal Data” Sigmod’17 Student Research Competition May 14- 19 2017, Chicago, Il,Usa
- Mapreduce With Hadoop For Simplified Analysis Of Big Data Ch. Shobha Rani Research Scholar Department Of Computer Science Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana Dr. B. Rama Assistant Professor Department Of Computer Science Volume 8, No. 5, May-June 2017 International Journal Of Advanced Research In Computer Science Research Paper Available Online At Www.Ijars.info © 2015-19, Ijars All Rights Reserved 853 Issn No. 0976-5697 Kakatiya University, Warangal, Telangana
- Open Source Big Data Analytics Technique: Ishan Sharma, Rajeev Tiwari And Abhineet Anand Raghavendra Kune1, Pramod Kumar Konugurthi1, Arun Agarwal,Raghavendra Rao Chillarige And Rajkumar Buyya:” Xhami – Extended Hdfs And Mapreduce Interface For Big Data Image Processing Applications In Cloud Computing Environments” Published Online 15

July 2016 In Wiley Online Library (Wileyonlinelibrary.Com). Doi: 10.1002/Spe.2525

Security Issues Associated With Big Data In Cloud Computing Venkata Narasimha Inukollu ,
Sailaja Arsi And Srinivasa Rao Ravuri department Of Computer Engineering, Texas Tech
University, Usa department Of Banking And Financial Services,Cognizant Technology
Solutions, India

Shobha Rani., Rama, B, ” Mapreduce With Hadoop For Simplified Analysis Of Big Data”
International Journal Of Advanced Research In Computer Science Volume 8, No. 5, May-
June 2017 Issn No. 0976-5697

Web Sources

http://www.ijeit.com/Vol%207/Issue%208/IJEIT1412201802_05.pdf

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/034b/0d609fe58e0ab0cbfa02b86e39dd41f2364a.pdf>

<https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/3e0a/548fae69482e550c21a6dc7806213203c3bc.pdf>

http://www.ijarse.com/images/fullpdf/1526041070_BVNC-36.pdf

<https://afourtech.com/integrating-mapreduce-with-hadoop-big-data/>

<http://pubs.sciepub.com/iteces/4/1/4/index.html>

http://paper.ijcsns.org/07_book/201702/20170219.pdf

<https://www.ijcsmc.com/docs/papers/June2016/V5I6201686.pdf>

<http://pubs.sciepub.com/iteces/4/1/4/index.html>

<http://www.ijarcsse.com/index.php/ijarcsse/article/view/58/0>